

The Relationship between Personal Traits, Travel Motivation, Perceived Value and Behavioural Intention of Tourists Participating in Adventure Activities*

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Abstract

The personality traits of tourists and their instinct to travel are seen as factors influencing their holiday purchase decisions. In addition, it is known that the attractiveness characteristics of destinations are factors affecting tourists before or during the holiday purchase decision. At this point, knowing the personality traits of tourists, the factors push them to travel, and the factors pull them to a certain destination are very important for destination management organizations and managers of tourism and adventure activity businesses that aim to attract tourists to their destinations or businesses.

In the scope of the research, an application has been carried out for tourists participating in adventure activities in Fethiye. Data were obtained from 405 tourists using the survey technique. As a result of the analysis, it was determined that there is a significant relationship between the personality traits and perceived value. In addition, it was found that there is a strong and significant relationship between the perceived value of tourists and their loyalty. Significant relationships were found between the perceived value of tourists and the factors pushing them to travel and pulling them to the destination. It has been found that there are significant relationships between the level of loyalty of tourists and the factors pushing them to travel and pulling them to the destination.

Keywords: Personal Traits, Travel Motivations, Perceived Value, Loyalty, Adventure Activities

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1. Introduction

Personality traits emerge as a very important concept for the service sector, which is based on human beings. In particular, the fact that the service producer and the beneficiary are human makes it much more important to determine the personality traits that contain very important clues about human psychology. In the tourism sector, which is a sub-branch of the service sector, services are offered to many people from different types of tourists. Being able to determine the personality traits of tourists from different nationalities, understanding the possible differences in personality traits among them and developing strategies in this direction is seen as an important advantage for all stakeholders providing services in the tourism sector.

People can travel for many different reasons. While some people may want to get away from the place where they live all the time and just rest and relax, another person may want to travel with different motives such as seeing new places, interact with different cultures or seeking adventure. The same is true for the attractiveness of tourist destinations. While some destinations can pull tourists with their natural beauties, some may be preferred by tourists because they are more accessible, contain more entertainment and activity opportunities, or create a more reliable destination perception. At this point, determining the factors that push people to travel is a very important information for destination managers who want to attract more tourists to their destination. This information will enable destination managers to perform their advertisements and promotions more effectively in the markets they address. Determining the attractive factors of the destination, which gives important information about why people choose a destination, is important in terms of determining which of the attractions of the destination is effective in the tourists' preference of the destination.

People's perspectives or perceptions towards any situation or event may differ. This is also true for people who buy any product or service. In particular, "heterogeneity" which is among the characteristics of the service, may cause different perceptions of the service at a similar level offered to different people by the same service employee. At this point, it is important to know what kind of value perception tourists have for the product or service they buy in the tourism sector, where the service is produced and offered intensively. A tourist with a positive perceived value for the product or service he/she buys will be more likely to exhibit positive behavioral intentions.

This research examines the relationship between personality traits, travel motivations (push and pull factors), perceived value and behavioral intention (loyalty) of tourists participating in adventure activities in the Fethiye region. Accordingly, this research consists of three main parts. The first part includes the literature review of the research. Second part includes the methodology of the research and finally third part includes the results, discussion and suggestions of the research.

2. Literature Review

Personal Traits

Personality is defined as a concept that can answer the underlying reasons of who people are and the behaviors they display (Mount, Barrick, Scullen and Rounds, 2005: 449). Cüceloğlu (2018: 401) expresses personality as a set of behaviors that distinguish people from each other and that people exhibit unique to them.

It is seen that many different personality theories (psychoanalytic, behavioral and cognitive, humanistic, distinctive trait, etc.) have emerged from past to present. Among these personality theories, the distinctive trait theory differs in that it is based on scientific research rather than subjective evaluations (Cüceloğlu, 2018: 416). It is known that the theory that is included within the scope of the differential trait theory and which is frequently used to determine personality traits in the literature is “Five Factor Personality Traits”. According to this theory, personality is explained in five basic dimensions. It is possible to list these dimensions as follows.

- *Extraversion*: It can be stated that people with these personality traits are friendly, full of energy, high adrenaline passion, love to socialize, enjoy spending time with other people, try to look at the positive side of events and are sociable (Störmer and Fahr, 2013: 2865)
- *Agreeableness*: It can be said that people with these personality traits are tolerant, exhibit altruistic behaviors, prone to cooperate, polite, try to stay away from conflicts, have an optimistic perspective on life in general, and are affectionate (Goldberg, 1990: 1220).
- *Conscientiousness*: It can be stated that people with these personality traits have high self-discipline, take care to act in a careful, orderly and planned manner, do not hesitate to take responsibility for the task they take, strive for success and show perseverance (Patrick, 2010: 241).
- *Emotional Stability*: It can be stated that people with these personality traits are quiet, compliant, avoiding to act in a hurry, patient, resistant to the difficulties they face, do not act impulsively and have a low tendency to feel anger (Robbins and Judge, 2007: 110).
- *Openness to Experience*: It can be said that people with these personality traits are prone to learning new things, brave, not afraid of spending personal time, curious, open to differences and new ideas (Cloninger, 2004: 242).

Travel Motivation

Motivation is seen as a very important variable that will contribute to understanding tourist behavior. Because the driving force behind people's behavior is motivation (Fodness, 1994: 555). Goldner and Ritchie (2009: 248) argue that the answer to the question of why tourists tend to travel is simple, and that scientists

researching travel motivation need to find out why tourists tend to have a certain travel experience. Travel motivations of tourists are expressed as the whole of the motivations that push the tourist to travel and choose the region where he or she wants to spend his or her holiday (Crompton, 1979: 409). Understanding the motivations that determine an individual's decision to take a vacation and choose one destination for another is critical to the marketing of a destination (Sulaiman and Wilson, 2019, 4).

Although there are many theories to determine the travel motivation of tourists, it is known that the most popular theory is the "push" and "pull" travel motivation theory (Yuan and McDonald, 1990: 42; Baloglu and Uysal, 1996: 32). According to the push and pull theory of motivation, there are some internal and external forces that direct individuals to travel (Uysal and Jurovski, 1994: 844).

Perceived Value

Perceived value can be defined as assigning a benefit to a product or service based on the subjective interpretations of what sacrifices an individual has endured to obtain this product in return for any product or service purchased (Monroe and Chapman, 1987: 193). According to Zeithaml (1988: 13), it is possible to collect the definitions formed in the minds of consumers regarding perceived value in four groups. According to these groups:

- Value is low price.
- Value is anything that is required of a product.
- Value is the quality the consumer gets for the price he or she pays.
- Value is what the consumer receives in return for what they give.

Behavioral Intention

Behavioral intention is defined as an indicator that consumers' relationship with any business from which they purchase a product or service is strengthened and that they will continue to maintain this relationship (Zeithaml, Berry and Parasuraman, 1996: 33). Behavioral intention is expressed as the determinant of whether consumers will continue to purchase products or services from any business or leave the relevant business (Lin and Hsieh, 2005, 1598). Behavioral intention is defined as an indicator of what kind of behavior the tourist with the potential to buy travel in the future will exhibit. Behavioral intentions include behaviors such as a consumer keeping a business in mind, requesting it again, or leaving the relevant business. If a consumer leaves a business, the business will have to create new demand. Promotion efforts made to attract new customers can bring an extra cost burden to the business. For this reason, it will be possible for businesses to keep their existing customers, providing a cost advantage (Zeithaml et al, 1996: 32).

Adventure Tourism

Adventure tourism has grown enormously in recent years. It is noteworthy that it has become an important niche in special interest tourism and is the fastest-

growing type of tourism (Williams and Soutar, 2009: 413). In the essence of adventure tourism, it can be stated that individuals who participate in adventure activities generally have feelings and behaviors such as adrenaline, excitement, fear, the desire to overcome difficulties, to achieve success, to take risks and to act bravely (Swarbrooke, Beard, Leckie and Pomfret, 2003: 7). Adventure tourism generally includes the travels people want to realize in order to carry out activities that involve risk, danger, excitement, and adrenaline (Kane and Tucker, 2004: 217). Adventure tourism includes activities such as rafting, kite surfing, jeep or ATV safari, mountain or rock climbing, abseiling, cave walking, diving, snorkelling, paragliding, surfing and bungee jumping (Buckley, 2006: 2; Weber, 2001: 365).

3. Methodology

Purpose of the Research

The purpose of this research is to reveal whether there is a relationship between the personality traits, travel motivation, perceived value and behavioral intention (loyalty) of tourists participating in adventure activities.

The Model and Hypothesis of the Research

Figure 1. The Model of the Research

The model created within the scope of the purpose of the research is shown in Figure 1. The model of the research consists of personality traits, perceived value, travel motivation (push and pull factors) and behavioral intention (loyalty) variables. The following hypotheses have been developed for the purpose and model of the research.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between the personality traits of tourists participating in adventure activities and their perceived value.

H₂: There is a significant relationship between the personality traits and loyalty of the tourists participating in adventure activities.

H₃: There is a significant relationship between the personality traits of tourists participating in adventure activities and the factors that push them to travel.

H₄: There is a significant relationship between the personality traits of the tourists participating in adventure activities and the factors that pull them to the destination.

H₅: There is a significant relationship between the perceived value and loyalty of tourists participating in adventure activities.

H₆: There is a significant relationship between the perceived value of tourists participating in adventure activities and the factors that push them to travel.

H₇: There is a significant relationship between the perceived value of the tourists participating in adventure activities and the factors that pull them to the destination.

H₈: There is a significant relationship between the factors pushing tourists participating in adventure activities to travel and their loyalty.

H₉: There is a significant relationship between the factors that pull tourists participating in adventure activities to the destination and their loyalty.

H₁₀: There is a significant relationship between the factors pushing tourists participating in adventure activities to travel and the factors that pull them to the destination.

Sampling

The convenience sampling method, one of the non-probability sampling methods, was used in the research. The sample of the research consists of tourists participating in adventure activities in the Fethiye region. Within the scope of the research, 405 valid questionnaires were obtained. 254 of the tourists that participated in the research are Turkish tourist and 151 are foreign tourists. Of the foreign tourists, 97 are British, 46 are German and 8 are tourists from other nationalities. In the first stage of the research, it was considered to use the quota sampling technique. In this direction, it was aimed to look at the differences between nationalities (Turkish, British, German and Russian) by reaching an equal number of tourists from different nationalities. However, in the implementation phase of the research, the flow of foreign tourists to the Fethiye region has decreased relatively due to the travel restrictions caused by the Covid-19 epidemic and the fears of the people about the virus. That's why the sampling technique of the research was updated as convenience sampling method.

Research Limitations

The most important limitation of the research is that the implementation process of the research coincided with a period when the Covid-19 pandemic is at a high level. Particularly in this period, the fact that citizens from different countries came to Turkey in relatively small numbers compared to previous years, created an

important limitation in finding foreign tourists in the Fethiye. In addition, it can be stated that the results of the research are limited to the opinions of tourists who participated in the adventure activities that could be reached and surveyed in the Fethiye region between April and October 2020.

Data Collection

Scales were created after a comprehensive literature review to measure the variables involved in the research. The Ten-item Personality Scale included in the questionnaire is a scale developed by Gosling Rentfrow and Swann (2003) to measure personality traits. This scale consists of five sub-dimensions as in the Five-Factor Personality Traits. The travel motivation scale (push and pull factors) was created by making use of travel motivation scales used in many studies in the literature (Baloglu and McCleary, 1999; Yoon and Uysal, 2005; Kim, Noh and Jogaratan, 2007; Jang and Cai, 2002; Heung, Qu and Chu, 2001). For the perceived value scale, questionnaire expressions were created by using more than one research (Sweeney and Soutar, 2001; Prebensen, Woo and Uysal, 2014; Williams and Soutar, 2009). Behavioral intention scale was created by making use of two studies. The "loyalty" dimension of the behavioral intention scale presented by Zeithaml, Berry, and Parasuraman (1996) was used. At the same time, a statement about the intention to buy again in the future from the research presented by Patterson and Spreng (1996) was used in the survey. Some questions were asked to determine the demographic characteristics of the participants in the survey. 5-point Likert type was used for the scale questions that make up the questionnaire form. Participants were asked to mark their level of participation regarding the expressions in the questionnaire form as "1-strongly disagree, 2-disagree, 3-neither agree nor disagree, 4- agree and 5-strongly agree".

Findings

Descriptive Analysis of the Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

In this section, descriptive analyses regarding the socio-demographic characteristics of the individuals participating in the research are included.

According to Table 1, it is seen that 51.4% of the participants were male; 48.4% are married; 36.8% of them are in the 25-34 age range, 56.8% has bachelor degree 62.7% are domestic tourists and 16.31% are self-employed. At the same time, it is seen that %36,8 of the tourists participating in the research are paragliding.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Tourists

Variables	Group	n	%
Gender	Male	208	51,4
	Female	197	48,6
Marital Status	Single	180	44,4
	Married	196	48,4
	Other	29	7,2
Age	Lower than 18	5	1,2
	18-24	34	8,4
	25-34	149	36,8
	35-44	138	34,1
	45-54	62	15,3
Education Status	Higher than 55	17	4,2
	Primary School	4	1,0
	High School	51	12,6
	Associate Degree	50	12,3
	Bachelor Degree	230	56,8
Adventure Activities in which Tourists Participated	Postgraduate Degree	70	17,3
	Paragliding	149	36,8
	Diving	84	20,7
	Jeep Safari	58	14,3
	ATV Safari	57	14,1
	Rafting	50	12,3
Tourist Type	Other	7	1,7
	Domestic (Turkish)	254	62,7
Occupation	Foreign	151	37,3
	My Own Business	66	16,31
	Civil Servant	64	15,80
	Manager	57	14,07
	Teacher	54	13,33
	Academician	45	11,11
	Retired	41	10,12
	Student	37	9,14
	Housewife	11	2,71
	Unemployed	6	1,48
Total	Other	24	5,93
		405	100

Factor Analysis

In this part of the research, the results of the exploratory factor analyses of scales used in the research are shown.

Table 2: Personality Traits Scale Factor Analysis

Sub-Dimension	Expressions	Factor Load	Explained Variance	Eigenvalue
Extraversion	I see myself as an extraverted, enthusiastic.	0,923	28,762	2,876
	I see myself as a reserved, quiet.*	0,934		
Agreeableness	I see myself as a critical, quarrelsome.*	0,945	16,415	1,641
	I see myself as a sympathetic, warm.	0,946		
Conscientiousness	I see myself as a dependable, self-disciplined.	0,885	11,207	1,121
	I see myself as a disorganized, careless.*	0,917		
Emotional Stability	I see myself as anxious, easily upset.*	0,938	12,675	1,268
	I see myself as a calm, emotionally stable.	0,935		
Openness to Experience	I see myself as open to new experiences, complex.	0,935	2,048	20,482
	I see myself as a conventional, uncreative.*	0,948		
Total Variance	KMO Sampling Adequacy Measure: 0,564 Chi Square Value: 2153,525 Df: 45 Significance: 0,000		89,541	

* Indicates reverse coded items.

According to Table 2, as a result of the KMO and Barlett test ($p=0.00<0.05$), it was determined that there was a relationship between the statements included in the factor analysis. As a result of the analysis, the KMO value was found to be 0.564. According to this value, it is seen that the personality traits scale is a valid scale. As a result of the factor analysis applied to the personality traits scale, the expressions were gathered under 5 factors with a total explained variance of 89,541%.

Table 3: Travel Motivation Scale (Push Factors) Factor Analysis

Sub-Dimension	Expressions	Factor Load	Explained Variance	Eigenvalue
Seek Adventure	To be adventurer	0,853	38,771	10,856
	To try a new adventure activity.	0,795		
	To improve my knowledge about adventure activities	0,761		
	To find excitement.	0,772		
	To improve my abilities	0,544		
Need for Status Enhancement	To go to a place where my friends haven't been before	0,884	10,627	2,976
	To tell my friends about my journey	0,847		
	To increase my social status	0,825		
	To enhance my self-confidence	0,659		
	To get ready new stages in my life	0,549		
Seek Novelty	To thrive intellectually	0,656	4,702	1,317
	To experience different culture and lifestyles	0,733		
	To be there new/different places	0,673		
	To learn new things	0,504		
	To discover me.	0,409		
Escape and Relief	To renew mentally	0,817	5,229	1,464
	To relax physically	0,771		
	Getting away from routine life.	0,737		
	Getting away from stress and tension	0,725		
	Getting away from crowded	0,593		
	To be intertwined with nature.	0,557		
Socialization	To develop a close friendship	0,823	7,383	2,067
	To meet with new people	0,808		
	To meet people with similar interests	0,684		
	To be free and independent	0,581		
	To interact with local people	0,562		
Having a Pleased Time	To have a great time with other people (acquaintance, friend, etc.)	0,771	3,984	1,116
	To have fun	0,488		
Total Variance	KMO Sampling Adequacy Measure: 0,913 Chi Square Value: 8629,489 Df: 378 Significance: 0,000		70,696	

According to Table 3, as a result of the KMO and Barlett test ($p=0.00<0.05$), it was determined that there was a relationship between the statements included in the factor analysis. As a result of the analysis, the KMO value was found to be 0.913. This value shows that the push factors scale is a valid scale. As a result of the factor analysis applied to the push factors scale, the statements were gathered under 6 dimensions with a total explained variance of 70,696%.

Table 4: Travel Motivation Scale (Pull Factors) Factor Analysis

Sub-Dimension	Expressions	Factor Load	Explained Variance	Eigenvalue
Facilities of Destination	Possibility of integrating with different cultures	0,799	34,404	4,817
	Group activity opportunities	0,793		
	Presence of adventurous activities	0,786		
	Friendliness of people	0,646		
	Impact of social media	0,561		
	Good value for money	0,497		
Natural Beauties and Climate	Nice view and presence of natural attractiveness	0,857	13,439	1,881
	Nice climate	0,821		
	Untainted and unsoiled environment	0,762		
	Fresh air	0,604		
Security, Accessibility and Atmosphere	Not to feel a personal security problem	0,799	8,201	1,148
	Convenient transportation possibilities	0,620		
	Entertainment facilities	0,548		
	Presence of exotic atmosphere	0,468		
Total Variance	KMO Sampling Adequacy Measure: 0,839 Chi Square Value: 2061,439 Df: 91 Significance: 0,000		56,043	

According to Table 4, as a result of the KMO and Barlett test ($p=0.00<0.05$), it was determined that there was a relationship between the statements included in the factor analysis. As a result of the analysis, the KMO value was found to be 0.839. This value indicates that the pull factors scale is a valid scale. As a result of the factor analysis applied to the pull factors scale, the expressions are gathered under 3 dimensions with a total explained variance of 56,043%.

Table 5: Perceived Value Scale Factor Analysis

Sub-Dimension	Expressions	Factor Load	Explained Variance	Eigenvalue
Functional Value	The company organizing this adventure activity has a consistent quality.	0,825	15,421	0,808
	The company organizing this adventure activity has done well.	0,764		
	The company organizing this adventure activity has an acceptable standard of quality.	0,785		
	The company organizing this adventure activity is well organized.	0,629		
Value for Money	I got my money's worth in this adventure activity.	0,784	20,397	1,296
	This adventure activity offered me good value for money.	0,798		
	This adventure activity was a good one for the price paid.	0,833		
	This adventure activity is reasonably priced.	0,800		
Emotional Value	This adventure activity gave me feelings of well-being.	0,799	25,365	4,383
	This adventure activity was exciting.	0,859		
	This adventure activity made me satisfied.	0,817		
	This adventure activity made me feel happy.	0,794		
	This adventure activity made me feel adventurous.	0,861		
	This adventure activity provided an authentic experience for me.	0,718		
Social Value	This adventure activity gives social approval from others.	0,928	26,199	10,989
	This adventure activity makes me feel acceptable to others.	0,945		
	This adventure activity improves the way how I perceive.	0,809		
	This adventure activity contributes a better impression to me on other people.	0,950		
	This adventure activity makes me feel more socially accepted.	0,947		
	This adventure activity enables me to impress others.	0,904		
Total Variance	KMO Sampling Adequacy Measure: 0,945 Chi Square Value: 11304,809 Df: 190 Significance: 0,000		87,381	

According to Table 5, as a result of the KMO and Barlett test ($p=0.00<0.05$), it was determined that there was a relationship between the statements included in the factor analysis. As a result of the analysis, the KMO value was found to be 0.945. This value indicates that the perceived value scale is a valid scale. As a result of the factor analysis applied to the perceived value scale, the expressions are gathered under 4 dimensions with a total explained variance of 87,381%.

Table 6: Behavioral Intention (Loyalty) Scale Factor Analysis

Sub-Dimension	Expressions	Factor Load	Explained Variance	Eigenvalue
Loyalty	I say positive things about this adventure activity to other people.	0,930	81,641	4,898
	I recommend this adventure activity to other people.	0,947		
	I encourage my friends and relatives participating in this adventure activity.	0,953		
	This company will be my first choice to buy adventure activity services.	0,881		
	I would like to repeat this adventure activity.	0,875		
	I would go on other adventure activities in the future.	0,828		
Total Variance	KMO Sampling Adequacy Measure: 0,919 Chi Square Value: 2733,434 Df: 15 Significance: 0,000		81,641	

According to Table 6, as a result of the KMO and Barlett test ($p=0.00<0.05$), it was determined that there was a relationship between the statements included in the factor analysis. As a result of the analysis, the KMO value was found to be 0.919. This value shows that the behavioral intention (loyalty) scale is a valid scale. The explained variance value of the loyalty scale was found to be 81,641%.

Reliability Analysis

In this part of the research, the results of the reliability analysis of the scales that used in research are given. In this research, the Cronbach Alpha method is used for reliability analysis. It is possible to express the Cronbach Alpha (α) value interpretation as follows (Ural & Kilic, 2006: 286).

- $0,00 \leq \alpha \leq 0,40$ not reliable,
- $0,40 \leq \alpha \leq 0,60$ low reliable,
- $0,60 \leq \alpha \leq 0,80$ quite reliable,
- $0,80 \leq \alpha \leq 1,00$ high reliable.

According to Table 7, it is seen that the personality traits scale ($\alpha= 0,705$) is quite reliable. At the same time, it is noteworthy that the scales of travel motivation (Push Factors- $\alpha= 0,936$; Pull Factors- $\alpha= 0,841$), perceived value ($\alpha= 0,947$) and behavioral intention (loyalty) ($\alpha= 0,950$) are highly reliable scales.

Table 7: Reliability Analysis Results of the Scales Used in the Research

	Cronbach Alpha (α) Coefficient	Number of Expressions
Personal Traits	0,705	10
• Extraversion	0,903	2
• Agreeableness	0,895	2
• Conscientiousness	0,812	2
• Emotional Stability	0,878	2
• Openness to Experience	0,903	2
Travel Motivation (Push Factors)	0,936	28
• Seek Adventure	0,929	5
• Need for Status Enhancement	0,883	5
• Seek Novelty	0,855	5
• Escape and Relief	0,788	6
• Socialization	0,909	5
• Having a Pleasured Time	0,500	2
Travel Motivation (Pull Factors)	0,841	14
• Facilities of Destination	0,817	6
• Natural Beauties and Climate	0,798	4
• Security, Accessibility and Atmosphere	0,621	4
Perceived Value	0,947	20
• Functional Value	0,955	4
• Value for Money	0,967	4
• Emotional Value	0,957	6
• Social Value	0,967	6
Behavioral Intention	0,950	6
• Loyalty	0,950	6

Normality Test

In this section, the results of the normality analysis made regarding whether the scales used in the research show a normal distribution are given.

Table 8: Normality Test of Scales Used in the Research

Scale	Skewness	Kurtosis
Personality Traits	-,668	,539
Travel Motivation (Push Factors)	-,262	-,687
Travel Motivation (Pull Factors)	-,165	-,696
Perceived Value	-,763	,269
Behavioral Intention (Loyalty)	-1,294	1,075

According to George and Mallery (2020: 115), the fact that the Skewness and Kurtosis values, which emerged as a result of the normality analysis, are between +2.00 and -2.00 indicates that the relevant scales show a normal distribution. As seen in Table 8, the Skewness and Kurtosis values of all scales used in this study are between +2.00 and -2.00. This result indicates that the scales used

in the research show a normal distribution and that parametric tests will be used in the analyses to be made within the scope of the research.

Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis is a statistical analysis method that is widely used to determine whether there is a relationship between two variables, and the direction and strength of the relationship (Yazicioglu and Erdogan, 2014: 335). Correlation analyses are performed in various ways. It is known that the scales used in this study show a normal distribution as a result of the analysis of normality tests. For this reason, Pearson Correlation analysis method, which is a parametric test, is used in the correlation analysis to be carried out within the scope of the research.

Table 9: The Interpretation of the Pearson Correlation Coefficient

r*	Definition of Relationship
0,00-0,25	Very Weak
0,26-0,49	Weak
0,50-0,69	Moderate
0,70-0,89	High
0,90-1,00	Very High

*r: The Coefficient of the Pearson Correlation

The answer to the question of whether there is a significant relationship between the X and Y variables can be revealed through the correlation analysis method. The interpretation of the Pearson Correlation coefficient is shown below (Kalayci, 2005: 116).

The results of the Pearson correlation analysis performed to determine the relationship between personality traits and perceived value are given in Table 10.

Table 10: Results of Correlation Analysis Between Personality Traits and Perceived Value

N=405		Extraversion	Agreeableness	Conscientiousness	Emotional Stability	Openness to Experience
Functional Value	R	,233**	,296**	,067	,065	,064
Value for Money	R	,228**	,261**	,056	-,014	,078
Emotional Value	R	,306**	,284**	,170**	,203**	,111*
Social Value	R	,101*	,043	-,050	-,070	,085

* The correlation is significant at the 0.05 level. (2-tailed)

**The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level. (2-tailed)

When Table 10 is interpreted in general, it is seen that there is a partial relationship between the two scale sub-dimensions, and the existing relationships are at a very weak or weak level. It is seen that the most significant relationship between the variables is between “extraversion” and “emotional value” sub-dimensions. ($r=0.306$; $p<0.01$). In this direction, it can be said that the “ H_1 : There is a significant relationship between the personality traits of tourists participating in adventure activities and their perceived value.” is partially supported.

The results of the Pearson correlation analysis performed to determine the relationship between personality traits and behavioral intention (loyalty) are given in Table 11.

Table 11: Results of Correlation Analysis Between Personality Traits and Behavioral Intention (Loyalty)

N=405		Extraversion	Agreeableness	Conscientiousness	Emotional Stability	Openness to Experience
Loyalty	R	,314**	,282**	,124*	,121*	,121*

* The correlation is significant at the 0.05 level. (2-tailed)

**The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level. (2-tailed)

When Table 11 is examined, it is seen that there is a generally positive and significant relationship between all sub-dimensions of personality traits and behavioral intention (loyalty) dimension. In this direction, it can be said that the “*H₂: There is a significant relationship between the personality traits and loyalty of the tourists participating in adventure activities.*” is supported.

The results of the Pearson correlation analysis performed to determine the relationship between personality traits and push factors are given in Table 12.

Table 12: Results of Correlation Analysis Between Personality Traits and Push Factors

N=405		Extraversion	Agreeableness	Conscientiousness	Emotional Stability	Openness to Experience
Seek Adventure	R	,366**	,147**	,095	-,145**	,146**
Need for Status Enhancement	R	,115*	-,004	-,031	-,124*	,126*
Seek Novelty	R	,255**	,115*	,062	-,179**	,131**
Escape and Relief	R	,080	,096	,137**	,106*	,063
Socialization	R	,353**	,211**	,097	-,076	,181**
Having a Pleased Time	R	,295**	,124*	,238**	,418**	,130**

* The correlation is significant at the 0.05 level. (2-tailed)

**The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level. (2-tailed)

When Table 12 is examined, it is noteworthy that the "having a pleased time" sub-dimension has a positive and significant relationship with all sub-dimensions of personality traits. It is seen that the highest level of correlation coefficient value is between "having a pleased time" sub-dimension and "emotional stability" ($r=0.418$; $p<0.01$) sub-dimension. When the correlation analysis results in Table 12 are evaluated, it can be said that the “*H₃: There is a significant relationship between the personality traits of tourists participating in adventure activities and the factors that push them to travel.*” is partially supported.

The results of the Pearson correlation analysis performed to determine the relationship between personality traits and pull factors are given in Table 13.

Table 13: Results of Correlation Analysis Between Personality Traits and Pull Factors

N=405		Extraversion	Agreeableness	Conscientiousness	Emotional Stability	Openness to Experience
Facilities of Destination	R	,321**	,163**	,037	-,147**	,113*
Natural Beauties and Climate	R	,132**	,109*	,057	,049	-,039
Security, Accessibility and Atmosphere	R	,243**	,267**	,107*	,086	,060

* The correlation is significant at the 0.05 level. (2-tailed)

**The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level. (2-tailed)

According to Table 13, it can be stated that "extraversion" and "agreeableness" sub-dimensions have a positive and significant relationship with all sub-dimensions of pull factors. The correlation coefficient in these relationships shows that there is a very weak and weak relationship between the related sub-dimensions. When the correlation analysis results in Table 13 are evaluated, it can be said that the "*H₄: There is a significant relationship between the personality traits of the tourists participating in adventure activities and the factors that pull them to the destination.*" is partially supported.

The results of the Pearson correlation analysis performed to determine the relationship between perceived value and behavioral intention (loyalty) are given in Table 14.

Table 14: Results of Correlation Analysis Between Perceived Value and Behavioral Intention (Loyalty)

N=405		Functional Value	Value for Money	Emotional Value	Social Value
Loyalty	R	,756**	,801**	,884**	,321**

* The correlation is significant at the 0.05 level. (2-tailed)

**The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level. (2-tailed)

When Table 14 is examined, it is seen that the "loyalty" sub-dimension has a positive and significant relationship with all sub-dimensions of the perceived value scale. It is seen that this relationship between the "loyalty" sub-dimension and the "functional value" ($r= 0.756$; $p<0.01$) sub-dimension is high level. It is noteworthy that there is a very high level of relationship between the sub-dimensions of "value for money" ($r= 0.801$; $p<0.01$) and "emotional value" ($r= 0.884$; $p<0.01$). In this direction, it can be said that the "*H₅: There is a significant relationship between the perceived value and loyalty of tourists participating in adventure activities.*" is supported.

The results of the Pearson correlation analysis performed to determine the relationship between perceived value and push factors are given in Table 15.

Table 15: Results of Correlation Analysis Between Perceived Value and Push Factors

N=405		Functional Value	Value for Money	Emotional Value	Social Value
Seek Adventure	R	,323**	,459**	,368**	,297**
Need for Status Enhancement	R	,190**	,266**	,213**	,790**
Seek Novelty	R	,235**	,355**	,272**	,400**
Escape and Relief	R	,226**	,239**	,234**	,245**
Socialization	R	,207**	,333**	,302**	,408**
Having a Pleased Time	R	,333**	,285**	,482**	,220**

* The correlation is significant at the 0.05 level. (2-tailed)

**The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level. (2-tailed)

According to Table 15, there is a positive and significant relationship between all sub-dimensions of the perceived value scale and all sub-dimensions of the push factors scale. In particular, the relationship between the "need for status enhancement" sub-dimension and the "social value" sub-dimension ($r= 0.790$; $p<0.01$) is high. When the correlation analysis results in Table 15 are evaluated, it can be said that the "*H₆: There is a significant relationship between the perceived value of tourists participating in adventure activities and the factors that push them to travel.*" is supported.

The results of the Pearson correlation analysis performed to determine the relationship between perceived value and pull factors are given in Table 16.

Table 16: Results of Correlation Analysis Between Perceived Value and Pull Factors

N=405		Functional Value	Value for Money	Emotional Value	Social Value
Facilities of Destination	R	,414**	,546**	,438**	,485**
Natural Beauties and Climate	R	,364**	,345**	,387**	,124*
Security, Accessibility and Atmosphere	R	,409**	,476**	,488**	,190**

* The correlation is significant at the 0.05 level. (2-tailed)

**The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level. (2-tailed)

According to Table 16, there is a positive and significant relationship between all sub-dimensions of the perceived value scale and all sub-dimensions of the pull factors scale. In particular, it is seen that there is a moderate relationship between the sub-dimensions of "value for money" and "facilities of destination" ($r= 0.546$; $p<0.01$). When the correlation analysis results in Table 16 are investigated, it can be said that the "*H₇: There is a significant relationship between the perceived value of the tourists participating in adventure activities and the factors that pull them to the destination.*" is supported.

The results of the Pearson correlation analysis performed to determine the relationship between push factors and behavioral intention (loyalty) are given in Table 17.

Table 17: Results of Correlation Analysis Between Push Factors and Behavioral Intention (Loyalty)

N=405		Seek Adventure	Need for Status Enhancement	Seek Novelty	Escape and Relief	Socialization	Having a Pleased Time
Loyalty	R	,425**	,293**	,355**	,298**	,350**	,402**

* The correlation is significant at the 0.05 level. (2-tailed)

**The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level. (2-tailed)

When Table 17 is examined, it is seen that there is a positive and significant relationship between the behavioral intention (loyalty) scale and all sub-dimensions of the push factors scale. In this direction, it can be said that the “*H₈: There is a significant relationship between the factors pushing tourists participating in adventure activities to travel and their loyalty.*” is supported.

The results of the Pearson correlation analysis performed to determine the relationship between pull factors and behavioral intention (loyalty) are given in Table 18.

Table 18: Results of Correlation Analysis Between Pull Factors and Behavioral Intention (Loyalty)

N=405		Facilities of Destination	Natural Beauties and Climate	Security, Accessibility and Atmosphere
Loyalty	R	,488**	,410**	,458**

* The correlation is significant at the 0.05 level. (2-tailed)

**The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level. (2-tailed)

When Table 18 is investigated, it is seen that there is a positive and significant relationship between the behavioral intention (loyalty) scale and all sub-dimensions of the pull factors scale. In this direction, it can be said that the “*H₉: There is a significant relationship between the factors that pull tourists participating in adventure activities to the destination and their loyalty.*” is supported.

The results of the Pearson correlation analysis performed to determine the relationship between push factors and pull factors are given in Table 19. When Table 19 is examined, it is seen that there is a positive and significant relationship between all sub-dimensions of the push factors scale and all sub-dimensions of the pull factors scale. Especially, it is noteworthy that the relationships between “facilities of destination” and “seek adventure” ($r= 0,778$; $p<0,01$); socialization ($r= 0,718$; $p<0,01$); “seek novelty” ($r= 0,714$; $p<0,01$) are high. In this direction, it can be said that the “*H₁₀: There is a significant relationship between the factors pushing tourists participating in adventure activities to travel and the factors that pull them to the destination.*” is supported.

Table 19: Results of Correlation Analysis Between Push Factors and Pull Factors

N=405		Facilities of Destination	Natural Beauties and Climate	Security, Accessibility and Atmosphere
Seek Adventure	R	,778**	,283**	,437**
Need for Status Enhancement	R	,596**	,175**	,289**
Seek Novelty	R	,714**	,285**	,373**
Escape and Relief	R	,228**	,246**	,292**
Socialization	R	,718**	,177**	,411**
Having a Pleasured Time	R	,325**	,272**	,385**

* The correlation is significant at the 0.05 level. (2-tailed)

**The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level. (2-tailed)

4. Results and Discussion

In this research, the relationship between personality traits, travel motivations (push and pull factors), perceived value and behavioral intentions (loyalty) of tourists participating in adventure activities in Fethiye region is examined. The results of the research in the light of the data obtained from a total of 405 tourists participating in adventure activities in the Fethiye region are given below.

As a result of the analysis made in the research, it was determined that there is a positive and significant relationship between the extraversion personality trait and the perceived value. According to this result; it can be stated that the perceived value of tourists who have more extroverted personality traits is higher. In other words, it can be said that tourists who see themselves as extroverted, enthusiastic, sociable and enjoy socializing with others perceive more value positively from their adventure activity. Ju, Song, and Kim (2018) also reached similar results in their research.

Another result obtained as a result of the analyses is that there is a positive and significant relationship between the extraversion and agreeableness personality traits of the tourists participating in adventure activities and their loyalty. According to this result, it can be said that tourists who have more extroverted and agreeable personality traits have more loyalty. In other words, it can be stated that tourists who see themselves as willing, sociable, enjoying socializing, sympathetic, warm, away from fighting and criticizing show more loyalty. Jani and Han (2015) and Forrester, Taschian, and Shore (2016) also obtained similar results in their research.

An analysis was made to determine whether there is a significant relationship between the personality traits of tourists participating in adventure activities and the factors that push them to travel. As a result of this analysis, a positive and significant relationship was found between “having a pleased time”, which is one of the sub-dimensions of the factors that push tourists to travel, and personality traits. It can be stated that especially tourists with emotional stability personality traits have a travel motivation to spend more pleasant time. Abbate and Di Nuovo (2013) also reached similar results.

Another result of the research is that there are positive and significant relationships between the personality traits of the tourists participating in adventure activities and the factors that pull them to the destination. According to this result, it can be stated that tourists who have more extraversion and agreeableness personality traits take more into account the pull factors of the destination such as the facilities of the destination they will visit, its natural beauties, climate, safety, accessibility and atmosphere.

Another result of the research is that there is a positive and significant relationship between the perceived value of tourists participating in adventure activities and their loyalty. William and Soutar (2009), Gallarza and Saura (2006), Dalgic and Birdir (2015), Altunel and Gunlu (2015), Arpacı and Batman (2015) found similar results in their research. According to this result, the high value perceived by the tourists in functional, monetary, emotional and social terms contributes to the increase in their loyalty. Especially the high emotional and monetary value perceived by the tourists participating in adventure activities can lead to more loyal tourists. As it is known, Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs has been developed by discussing over time, taking into account that people have different needs. Thus, it was accepted to add three different needs (the need to know and understand, the need for aesthetics, the need for superiority) to Maslow's theory. Among these added needs, especially the need for "superiority" comes after the need for "self-actualization" and means "helping other people to realize themselves". From this point of view, the tourist's recommending the adventure activity he/she participates in to others and trying to encourage others to participate in this adventure activity can be interpreted as an attitude he/she exhibits towards meeting the need for "superiority".

The finding of significant relationships between the perceived value of tourists participating in adventure activities and the factors that push them to travel is another result of the research. In particular, it can be stated that tourists who travel with the motivation of needing to enhance their status have a higher perceived social value in their adventure activities. When this situation is evaluated in terms of the idea that individuals will gain more respect by increasing their status, it can be interpreted as a motivation for meeting the "esteem" in Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs. Another result is that tourists, who have more adventure-seeking motivation, have a high perceived monetary value in their adventure activities. Adventure seeking motivation can be expressed as a motivation that the individual internalizes in order to discover and prove herself/himself. From this point of view, it is possible to evaluate the motivation for seeking adventure within the scope of the "need for self-actualization" in Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs. In addition, it can be said that tourists, who have more motivation to spend their time, have more emotional value perceived in their adventure activities. It can be stated that tourists, who have more socialization and innovation-seeking motivations, have more perceived social value in their adventure activities.

It is seen that there is a significant relationship between the perceived value of tourists participating in adventure activities and the factors that pull them to destinations. In particular, it can be stated that the tourists who consider the destination facilities have higher perceived value. Redondo-Carretero, Camarero-Izquierde, Gutierrez-Arranz, and Rodriguez-Pinto (2017) reached similar results in

their research. It can be said that the tourists who travel by considering the destination's safety, accessibility and atmosphere have higher emotional, monetary and functional value.

A significant relationship was found between the factors that push the tourists participating in adventure activities to travel and their loyalty. It can be stated that tourists, who are more motivated to seek adventure and have a pleasant time, have higher loyalty levels. Dean and Suhartanto (2019) also reached similar results in their research.

It has been determined that there is a significant relationship between the factors that pull tourists participating in adventure activities to the destination and their loyalty. In particular, it can be said that tourists who travel by taking into account the destination possibilities more have higher loyalty.

As another result of the research, there is a significant relationship between the factors that push the tourists participating in adventure activities to travel and the factors that pull them to the destination. In this direction, it can be said that tourists, who are more motivated to seek adventure, enhance status, seek novelty and socialization, pay more attention to the facilities of the destination they will go to. In addition, it can be said that tourists, who are more motivated to seek adventure and socialization, take more into account the safety, accessibility atmosphere of destination they will go to.

The COVID-19 pandemic, which humanity has had to struggle with in recent days, is expected to affect people's understanding of travel. It can be stated that the desire of people not to be in crowded places and to stay away from such environments may reduce their motivation to participate in tourism events in masses. In this direction, it is estimated that people can participate in the tourism event more individually. This situation may also increase the interest in adventure tourism, where people can participate more individually.

This research aims to determine the relationships between personality traits, travel motivations (push and pull factors), perceived value and behavioral intention (loyalty) of tourists participating in adventure activities in Fethiye region. In future research, comparisons can be made by participating in different destinations with adventure activities. Research can be conducted for tourists participating in adventure activities by using different variables. In similar researches planned to be conducted in the future, it can be suggested to make comparisons between nationalities by obtaining data from tourists from different nationalities by quota sampling technique.

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